

Synthesis and Antimalarial Activity of Some New Quinazoline Derivatives

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Dialkylaminoalkylamino and dialkylaminomethylarylamino derivatives of quinazoline have been synthesised for their antimalarial activity.

QUINAZOLINE is 5:6-benzopyrimidine. Pyrimidine derivatives including those with condensed ring systems occupy a very important place in the metabolism of plants, animals and microorganisms. The fusion of a benzene ring to a heterocyclic system, as for example in quinazoline, offers certain more advantages: (a) the benzene ring can be suitably substituted in four positions in quinazoline and such substitutions in a variety of cases can bring about valuable changes from the point of view of therapeutic activity, e.g. presence of OCH_3 group in quinine and atebirin, Cl in atebirin and chloroquine, 2NH_2 groups in proflavin and 2CH_3 groups in antrypol (germanin) is very important, (b) replacement of a heterocyclic ring by benzene is important from the point of view of essential metabolite-antimetabolite relationship, e.g. adenine is an essential metabolite whereas benzimidazole is its antimetabolite.

A heterocyclic ring like quinoline or acridine attached with a dialkylaminoalkylamino and dialkylaminomethylamino chain as in chloroquine¹⁻³, atebirin⁴ and camoquine⁵ is conducive to good antimalarial activity. Isofebrifugine and febrifugine, the alkaloids containing quinazoline ring system, isolated from *Dichroa febrifuga* Lour, show antimalarial activity against *P. gallinaceum*⁶. In the present communication, synthesis of some new quinazoline derivatives of general structures I and II and antimalarial activity of some of these compounds have been reported.

The compounds were synthesised by known procedures by condensing⁷ substituted 3:1:4-benzoxazones⁸ with appropriate amines⁹. The halogenated anthranilic acids were prepared by the reported method¹⁰.

Two compounds, namely, 2-*p*-chloroanilino-4-(3'-*N*-diethylaminomethyl-4'-methoxy) quinazoline dihydrochloride (II_m) and 2-*p*-chloroanilino-4-(3'-*N*-diethylaminomethyl-4'-ethoxy) quinazoline dihydrochloride (II_q) were tested for antimalarial activity against *P. gallinaceum* in chicks (Table 1) at National Institute of Communicable Diseases, Delhi.

The following three compounds were sent to J. N. Medical College, Aligarh for the evaluation

- I
- a, X = Y = H, R' = Et, R'' = NEt₂
 - b, X = Y = H, R' = Et, R'' = NMe₂
 - c, X = Y = H, R' = Et, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - d, X = Y = H, R' = Me, R'' = NEt₂
 - e, X = Y = H, R' = Me, R'' = NMe₂
 - f, X = Y = H, R' = Me, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - g, X = Cl, Y = H, R' = Et, R'' = NEt₂
 - h, X = Cl, Y = H, R' = Et, R'' = NMe₂
 - i, X = Cl, Y = H, R' = Et, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - j, X = Cl, Y = H, R' = Me, R'' = NMe₂
 - k, X = Cl, Y = H, R' = Me, R'' = NEt₂
 - l, X = Cl, Y = H, R' = Me, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - m, X = Y = Cl, R' = Me, R'' = NMe₂
 - n, X = Y = Cl, R' = Me, R'' = NEt₂
 - o, X = Y = Cl, R' = Me, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - p, X = Y = Cl, R' = Et, R'' = NEt₂
 - q, X = Y = Cl, R' = Et, R'' = NMe₂
 - r, X = Y = Cl, R' = Et, R'' = N(OH)₂

- II
- a, X = Y, R' = Me, R'' = NEt₂
 - b, X = Y, R' = Me, R'' = NMe₂
 - c, X = Y, R' = Me, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - d, X = Y, R' = Et, R'' = NEt₂
 - e, X = Y, R' = Et, R'' = NMe₂
 - f, X = Y, R' = Et, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - g, X = H, R' = Me, R'' = NMe₂
 - h, X = H, R' = Me, R'' = NEt₂
 - i, X = H, R' = Me, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - j, X = H, R' = Et, R'' = NEt₂
 - k, X = H, R' = Et, R'' = NMe₂
 - l, X = H, R' = Et, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - m, X = *p*-Chloroanilino, R' = Me, R'' = NMe₂
 - n, X = *p*-Chloroanilino, R' = Me, R'' = NEt₂
 - o, X = *p*-Chloroanilino, R' = Me, R'' = N(OH)₂
 - p, X = *p*-Chloroanilino, R' = Et, R'' = NEt₂
 - q, X = *p*-Chloroanilino, R' = Et, R'' = NMe₂
 - r, X = *p*-Chloroanilino, R' = Et, R'' = N(OH)₂

TABLE 1

Compd. no.	Dose in term of Q	Result against <i>P. gallinaceum</i>
II _m	4Q	active
	Q	inactive
II _q	1/4Q	inactive
	4Q	active
	Q	inactive
	1/4Q	inactive

of their antimalarial activity. The procedure adopted and the report (Table 2) of these compounds are given below.

TABLE 2

Compd. no.	Average % parasitemia
Ic	All animals died
Ig	10.2%
IVc	10.6%
Saline	20.6%
Chloroquine	8.8%

All the mice were inoculated with 10 million *Plasmodium berghei* parasitized mouse RBC. The blood smears of these animals were tested for the appearance of parasite. These animals were divided into 6 groups consisting of 6 animals each. All these animals were given different drugs at a dose 10 mg/kg body weight, for four days through subcutaneous route, starting on the day on which parasite appeared in the blood smear for the first time. Controls were treated with the normal saline only. On the day following the last dose of the drug, blood smears were made from each animal and stained with Leishman stain. The smears were examined for the parasitemia. The average percent parasitemia was calculated for each group. All the animals in the group treated with drug Ic died on the day following first dose of the drug.

Four compounds were tested for their antimalarial activity in the Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh. The following is the procedure adopted. Swiss albino male mice, 5-6 weeks old were inoculated intraperitoneally with 1×10^8 *Plasmodium berghei* infected red blood cells. Tail smears of the animals stained with Giemsa were tested for the appearance of the parasite. These animals were divided into seven groups consisting of 4-5 animals each. All these animals were given different drugs in the concentration 0.3 mg/0.1 ml per dose for three days intraperitoneally starting from the day when the animals showed a parasitemia of 3-5 percent. The control animals were treated with normal saline only. Chloroquine was taken as the control drug.

Compounds Ig, Ii, Iib and Iir were tested for antimalarial activity against *P. berghei* in mice, out of which Ig has shown promising results in arresting the growth of the parasite (Table 3).

TABLE 3

Compd. no.	Mean percentage parasitaemia		Percentage mortality			
	Before drug inoculation (day 3rd P.I.)	2 days after drug inoculation (day 7th P.I.)	5 days after drug inoculation (day 12th P.I.)	6th P.I.	10th P.I.	12th P.I.
Ig	4.1	0	25	—	25	75
Ii	5.0	4.0	35	—	—	67
Iib	5.0	6	all died	—	—	100
Iir	3.0	0	all died	—	50	50
Chloroquine	2.6	0	0	—	—	—
Control (without drug)	3.5	13.3	all died	25	50	25

P.I. = Post infection.

Further work on the evaluation of the various compounds is still in progress.

Experimental

2-Methyl-3-(3'-N-piperidinomethyl-4'-ethoxy)phenyl-4(3H)quinazoline Ic: A mixture of 1.6 g (0.01 mol) 2-methyl-3 : 1 : 4-benzoxazone and 2.44 g (0.01 mol) of 3-N-piperidino-methyl-4-ethoxy aniline was heated on water bath for 2 h. The mass obtained was washed with ether and filtered. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol to get Ic as white powder (1.2 g), m.p. 122-123° (Found : N, 11.0. $C_{22}H_{27}O_2N_3$ requires N, 11.14%); ν_{max} 3140, 2926, 2840, 1630, 1440, 1360, 1235, 770, 730, 700 cm^{-1} .

The remaining mass obtained from the mother liquor was treated with 5 ml perchloric acid and heated on a water bath for 1 h. The separated solid was filtered and dried. On crystallisation from a mixture of absolute alcohol and dry ether yielded the perchlorate salt of Ic as white powder (1 g), m.p. 148° (Found : N, 8.5. $C_{22}H_{27}O_2N_3 \cdot HClO_4$ requires N, 8.9%).

6,8-Dichloro-2-methyl-3-(3'-N-diethylaminomethyl-4'-methoxy)phenyl-4(3H)quinazolinone Iii: A mixture of 2.07 g (0.01 mol) 6,8-dichloro-2-methyl-3 : 1 : 4-benzoxazone and 2.11 g (0.01 mol) 3N-diethylaminomethyl-4-methoxy aniline was heated on a water bath for 2-3 h. The resulting mass was filtered and dried. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol as brown powder (1.9 g), m.p. 105° (Found : C, 61.01; H, 5.5; N, 10.2. $C_{21}H_{23}N_3O_2Cl_2$ requires C, 60.0; H, 5.47; N, 10.01%).

The other 2-methyl-3-(substituted)-4(3H)quinazolinones and 6-chloro-6,8-dichloro-2-methyl-3-(substituted)-4(3H)quinazolinones were prepared in a similar manner. Their m.p.s. yields, and analytical data are reported in Table 4.

4-Chloroquinazoline: 4-Quinazoline was obtained by heating anthranilic acid with excess of formamide¹¹. This was then refluxed with phosphorus

TABLE 4

Compd. no.	Mold. formula	M.p. °C	Analysis % . Found/(Calcd.)				Solvent for crystallisation*
			N	C	H	Cl	
Ia	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂	115-116	11.80 (11.50)				A
Ib	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂	95-96	12.50 (12.46)				AE
Ic	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂	122-123	11.00 (11.14)				A
Id	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂	135-136	11.95 (11.96)				A
Ie	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂	104-105	12.08 (12.00)				AE
If	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂	172	11.52 (11.57)				A
Ig	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	115-116	10.66 (10.50)	66.01 (66.08)	6.45 (6.50)		A
Ih	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	127-128	11.42 (11.30)	64.75 (64.60)	5.91 (5.92)		A
Ii	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	138	10.18 (11.20)	67.10 (67.07)	6.09 (6.31)		A
Ij	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	124-125	11.50 (11.70)				A
Ik	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	108-109	11.89 (10.95)	65.20 (65.36)	6.15 (6.22)		A
Il	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	120	10.66 (10.56)	66.12 (66.41)	6.01 (6.03)		A
Im	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	115-116	10.72 (10.71)	58.25 (58.16)	4.56 (4.48)		A
In	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	105	10.20 (10.00)	61.00 (60.00)	5.50 (5.47)	19.50 (19.90)	A
Io	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	107	9.60 (9.70)	62.00 (61.11)	5.28 (5.32)		A
Ip	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	135	9.80 (9.67)				A
Iq	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	120	10.14 (10.30)				A
Ir	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	245	9.52 (9.40)				B
Ith	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ ON ₂ .HCl	256	15.01 (15.03)	64.70 (64.42)	4.40 (6.44)		B
Ilg	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ ON ₂ .HCl	251-252	16.00 (16.25)				B
Ihi	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON ₂ .HCl	261-262	14.62 (14.56)	65.55 (65.53)	6.03 (6.24)		B
Ihj	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON ₂ .HCl	270-271	14.42 (14.48)				B
Ihk	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ ON ₂ .HCl	219-220	15.55 (15.62)				B
Iil	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ON ₂ .HCl	236-237	14.12 (14.05)	66.15 (66.24)	6.51 (6.52)		A
Iim	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ON ₂ .Cl.2HCl	252	13.50 (13.70)				A
Iin	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ON ₂ .Cl.2HCl	238-239	13.10 (13.00)				A
Iio	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON ₂ .Cl.2HCl	265-266	12.60 (12.80)				A
Iip	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ON ₂ .Cl.2HCl	245-246	12.50 (12.70)				A
Iiq	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ON ₂ .Cl.2HCl	272	13.30 (13.40)				A
Iir	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ON ₂ .Cl.2HCl	264	12.20 (12.60)				A
Iia	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ .2HCl	286	13.68 (13.65)				A
Iib	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ .2HCl	280	15.00 (15.02)			12.64 (12.60)	A
Iic	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ .2HCl	286	13.10 (13.14)			11.10 (11.11)	C
Iid	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ .2HCl	262	13.00 (13.06)			11.00 (11.04)	A
Iie	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ .2HCl	250	14.20 (14.31)			12.01 (12.09)	A
Iif	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ .2HCl	256	12.61 (12.59)			10.60 (10.64)	

* A = Absolute ethanol, B = Benzene, C = Ethanol, AE = Absolute ethanol-ether.

oxychloride and phosphorus pentachloride for 5.5 h. Phosphorus oxychloride was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with ammonia and extracted with ether. Ether was evaporated when 4-chloroquinazoline was obtained.

4-(3'-4-Piperidinomethyl-4-ethoxy)anilino quinazoline hydrochloride III: It was prepared by refluxing 2.88 g (0.02 mol) 4-chloroquinazoline and 4.96 g (0.02 mol) 3*N*-piperidino-methyl-4-ethoxy aniline for 3 h in the presence of 20 ml benzene. Benzene was then distilled off and the residue was filtered and dried. It was crystallised from benzene into a white powder (1.4 g), m.p. 236-237° (Found: C, 66.15; H, 6.51; N, 14.12. $C_{22}H_{26}ON_4 \cdot HCl$ requires C, 66.24; H, 6.52; N, 14.05%).

The other 4-substituted quinazolines were prepared similarly.

2-*p*-Chloroanilino-4-chloro-quinazoline: 2:4-Dihydroxy quinazoline¹² was refluxed with phosphorus oxychloride and phosphorus pentachloride to get 2:4-dichloroquinazoline which was then stirred with 2*N* sodium hydroxide solution to form 2-chloro-4-hydroxy quinazoline. This was then refluxed with chloroaniline, water, acetone and hydrochloric acid to form 2-*p*-chloroanilino-4-hydroxy quinazoline. 2-*p*-Chloroanilino-4-hydroxy quinazoline was refluxed with phosphorus oxychloride and phosphorus pentachloride to form 2-*p*-chloroanilino-4-chloroquinazoline.

2-*p*-Chloroanilino-4-(3'-*N*-dimethylamine-methyl-4-ethoxy)anilino quinazoline dihydrochloride IIg: It was prepared by heating 1.2 g (0.004 mol) 4-chloro-2-*p*-chloroanilinoquinazoline with 0.776 g (0.004 mol) 3-*N*-dimethylamino-methyl-4-ethoxy aniline in the presence of 5 ml glacial acetic acid on a water bath for 2 h. The solution was then diluted with 20 ml water, boiled and filtered and then 5 ml conc. hydrochloric acid was added to it. It was then allowed to stand for 2 h in an ice bath. The dihydrochloride separated out was dissolved in alcohol by boiling, charcoaled and filtered. Upon standing the desired compound separated as a white powder (0.75 g), m.p. 272° (Found: N, 13.3. $C_{25}H_{26}N_5OCl_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 13.4%).

The other 2-*p*-chloroanilino-4-substituted quinazolines were prepared similarly.

2:4-Di(3'-*N*-piperidino methyl-4'-ethoxyanilino)quinazoline dihydrochloride IIh: It was prepared by heating 0.796 g (0.004 mol) 2:4-dichloroquinazoline and 0.936 g (0.004 mol) 3-*N*-piperidinomethyl-4'-ethoxy aniline in the presence of dry benzene on a water bath for 2 h. The mass was chilled in ice when the desired product separated out. It was filtered, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol into yellow powder (0.45 g), m.p. 256° (Found: N, 12.61; Cl, 10.60. $C_{36}H_{46}N_6O_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 12.59; Cl, 10.64%).

The other 2:4-disubstituted quinazolines were prepared similarly.

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References

1. C. PRICH and M. ROYSTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1204.
2. E. A. STECK, L. L. HALLOCK and C. M. SUTER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **70**, 4063.
3. A. R. SURREY and H. F. HAMMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 1814.
4. P. N. NATARANJAN and LEN NGIAM TONG, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 829.
5. J. H. BURCKHALTER, F. H. TENDICK, E. M. JONES, P. A. JONES, W. F. HOLCOMB and A. L. RAWLINS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1363.
6. J. B. KOEPLI, J. A. BROCKMAN, JR. and J. MOFFAT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 8323.
7. P. SINGH and I. S. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 77.
8. D. T. ZENTMEYER and E. C. WAGNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, **14**, 967.
9. J. H. BURCKHALTER, F. H. TENDICK, E. M. JONES, P. A. JONES, W. F. HOLCOMB and A. L. RAWLINS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1371.
10. L. M. SHERRILL, E. ELISBERG and E. M. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1301.
11. L. M. SHERRILL, E. ELISBERG and E. M. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1300.
12. F. H. S. CURD, J. A. LANDQUIST and F. L. ROSE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 777.